

An Investigation on Photocatalytic and Antibacterial Performance of GO Based Ternary Nanocomposite under Visible Light Irradiation

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Abstract

A facile methodology for the synthesis of novel La₂CuO₄/CeO₂/rGO hybrid nanocomposite was demonstrated via solvothermal assisted homogeneous precipitation method. The phase, crystal structure, surface morphology and elemental composition of synthesized nanocomposite was characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) and High resolution transmission electron microscopy (HR-TEM). Absorption range and band gap energy were investigated by UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (UV-Vis DRS). The photocatalytic examination to degrade a target pollutant (Reactive Blue 160) and inactivation of both positive and negative bacterial strains in aqueous solution were investigated under the illumination of visible light. The combination of rGO with binary nanocomposites leads to a better photocatalytic and antibacterial performance than other bare synthesized materials. The enhanced photocatalytic and antibacterial activity of La₂CuO₄/CeO₂/rGO is promising for the further application of visible light driven photocatalyst in polluted water treatment.

Key words: Nanocomposite, rGO - Reduced Graphite oxide, Solvothermal, Photocatalyst, antibacterial activity.